

Appendix D

Co-occurrence tables for all categories of factors

Table of co-occurrence between human and organizational factors

Co-occurrence	Access management	International standards	Policies and regulations	Risk assessment	Threat modelling
Human behaviour	0	0	4	1	0
Psychological components	0	1	4	1	1
Cybersecurity awareness	6	3	19	6	2
Cybersecurity training	4	7	23	5	2
Knowledge	0	0	3	4	3

Table of co-occurrence between human and physical factors

Co-occurrence	Disabling unused physical ports	Hardening of IT infrastructure	Physical security of servers	Security design of organizational IT Infrastructure	Updates and patches
Human behaviour	0	0	0	0	0
Psychological components	0	0	0	0	0
Cybersecurity awareness	0	2	0	2	4
Cybersecurity training	1	3	0	4	10
Knowledge	0	0	0	1	1

Table of co-occurrence between organizational and physical factors

Co-occurrence	Disabling unused physical ports	Hardening of IT infrastructure	Physical security of servers	Security design of organizational IT Infrastructure	Updates and patches
Access management	0	3	2	0	8
International standards	0	1	0	2	3
Policies and regulations	0	1	0	3	6
Risk assessment	0	1	1	3	5
Threat modelling	0	0	0	0	0

Appendix D

Co-occurrence tables for all categories of factors

Table of co-occurrence between technological and physical factors

Co-occurrence	Human behaviour	Psychological components	Cybersecurity awareness	Cybersecurity training	Knowledge
AI (machine learning, deep learning)	0	3	0	0	2
Criptography (Data encryption)	0	0	6	7	1
IPS & IDS implementation	0	0	3	4	0
Multifactor authentications	0	0	1	4	0
Vulnerability management	0	1	1	4	2

Table of co-occurrence between technological and organizational factors

Co-occurrence	Access management	International standards	Policies and regulations	Risk assessment	Threat modelling
AI (machine learning, deep learning, transformers)	3	0	0	3	4
Criptography (Data encryption)	11	5	12	6	1
IPS & IDS implementation	6	2	2	5	2
Multifactor authentications	8	2	3	4	1
Vulnerability management	6	4	5	11	7

Table of co-occurrence between technological and physical factors

Co-occurrence	Disabling unused physical ports	Hardening of IT infrastructure	Physical security of servers	Security design of organizational IT Infrastructure	Updates and patches
AI (machine learning, deep learning, transformers)	0	0	1	0	2
Criptography (Data encryption)	2	2	1	2	12
IPS & IDS implementation	1	1	1	0	5
Multifactor authentications	0	1	2	2	3
Vulnerability management	0	2	1	0	7